

Base Isolation Technology for Seismic Resilience in Dhaka

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Abstract—Dhaka City faces significant earthquake risk due to high population density, unplanned urbanization, and the widespread construction of buildings without adequate seismic design. Even moderate seismic events can cause severe structural damage and loss of life. This study examines the effectiveness of seismic isolation pads in enhancing building safety and reducing earthquake-induced damage in Dhaka. An online survey in the form of google form was employed, combining a questionnaire-based survey of 30 respondents from different private Universities in Dhaka to assess earthquake awareness, preparedness, and public perception of seismic isolation technology, along with a review of relevant literature and seismic risk assessments. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods and thematic interpretation. The results reveal a high level of public concern regarding earthquake hazards and strong support for mandatory safety measures, although awareness of seismic isolation technology remains limited. The findings indicate that seismic isolation pads can significantly reduce seismic forces transmitted to structures, thereby improving structural performance during earthquakes. This study concludes that, with appropriate policy support, technical guidelines, and public awareness initiatives, seismic isolation technology offers an effective and economically viable solution for improving seismic resilience in Dhaka City.

Index Terms—Base isolation, building safety, seismic isolation, seismic resilience, urban earthquake risk.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background Information

Bangladesh is located in a seismically active region, and several studies have identified Dhaka City as highly vulnerable to earthquake hazards due to its dense population and rapid, unplanned urban development [1]. Many buildings in Dhaka were constructed before the enforcement of modern seismic design provisions, increasing the risk of severe structural damage during earthquakes [2]. Recent seismic events have highlighted the potential consequences of inadequate earthquake preparedness in the city [3]. Conventional building construction methods commonly used in Dhaka provide limited protection against strong ground motion. Even moderate earthquakes can cause significant damage to structures that are not designed or retrofitted for seismic resistance [4]. Consequently, there is a growing need for effective earthquake mitigation techniques applicable to both existing and new buildings. Seismic isolation technology, particularly base isolation systems, has been recognized as an effective method

for reducing seismic forces transmitted to structures. Studies conducted in low to moderate seismic regions demonstrate that base isolation can significantly reduce base shear and structural displacement, improving building performance during earthquakes [4], [5]. However, the application of this technology in Bangladesh remains limited due to factors such as cost, lack of awareness, and limited technical expertise [2].

B. Overview

This study evaluates the potential of seismic isolation pads to improve building safety and reduce earthquake damage in Dhaka City. Public awareness and perception were assessed through a questionnaire-based survey, supported by secondary seismic risk data. The research aims to provide insights into the feasibility and effectiveness of base isolation techniques in the context of Dhaka's urban environment.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Description of the solution

This study investigates earthquake awareness, preparedness, and perceptions of building safety among residents of Dhaka City. A mixed-methods approach was adopted to collect both primary and secondary data for a comprehensive understanding of seismic risks and community preparedness. Primary data were obtained through a structured online questionnaire designed to assess participants' knowledge, past experiences with seismic events, and perceptions of building safety. Secondary data were collected from newspaper articles, reliable online sources, and 12 existing earthquake preparedness questionnaires to supplement and refine the survey design.

B. Methods used

A structured questionnaire consisting of 12 items was created using Google Forms, including 9 multiple-choice questions, 1 close-ended question, and 2 open-ended questions. A pre-test was performed with a few students to check clarity and timing, and the questionnaire was subsequently polished. The survey was distributed online and completed by 30 participants, primarily private university students in Dhaka aged 18 to 25. Random sampling was used to ensure unbiased participation, and the survey was conducted over a period of one week. Secondary sources provided information on seismic risk profiles and construction safety guidelines. Reviewing existing earthquake preparedness questionnaires helped improve

question clarity and coverage. Quantitative responses were entered and cleaned in Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were calculated for categorical variables. Cross-tabulation was used to examine relationships between variables, such as building type and perceived risk. Qualitative responses were coded thematically to identify recurring patterns. Electronic informed consent was obtained at the start of the survey. Participants were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, and all data were securely stored and used solely for academic purposes.

C. Rationale of selecting participants

Participants were primarily private university students of Dhaka aged 18 to 25, representing a demographic likely to be engaged and responsive to online surveys. Random sampling was used to minimize bias and ensure the reliability of responses. The survey was distributed via Google Forms through social media, community groups, and email to reach a diverse set of participants. This sample size of 30 participants provided preliminary insights into awareness patterns, while the combination of primary and secondary data allowed for a more comprehensive analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result below shows that the majority of respondents are concerned or strongly concerned about earthquakes in Dhaka. This high level of anxiety is most likely caused by the city's large population, uncontrolled building, and history of seismic activity. The findings suggest that earthquakes are viewed as a severe hazard by the people.

be selected.

A. Results

Figure 1 shows that most individuals have witnessed or experienced an earthquake in Dhaka city.

Fig. 1. Number of people who have witnessed or experienced Earthquake

Figure 2 illustrates the extent of public awareness of seismic isolation pad technology. The results show that, while some respondents are familiar with this technology, a considerable proportion are unaware of its applicability in building safety. This emphasizes the importance of enhanced public education and awareness initiatives on current earthquake resistant technology in Dhaka.

Fig 2. Awareness of Seismic Isolation Pad Technology among Respondents

Figure 3 demonstrate varying understandings of appropriate earthquake safety procedures. While many respondents picked advised behaviors such as sheltering beneath a table or remaining in open spaces, some chose risky answers such as racing down stairs. This demonstrates a limited understanding of earthquake safety procedures and highlights the need for practical training and public exercises to enhance fast reaction behavior.

Fig 3. Initial Safety Actions Chosen by Respondents During an Earthquake.

The data below show that the public strongly supports making earthquake protection measures mandatory for all types of structures in Dhaka. Most respondents agreed or strongly agreed with this statement, indicating a rising concern about building safety and an understanding of the need of regulatory enforcement in reducing earthquake related damage and deaths.

Fig. 4. Public Opinion on Making earth safety measures mandatory in Dhaka

The result below shows that the majority of respondents are concerned or strongly concerned about earthquakes in Dhaka. This high level of anxiety is most likely caused by the city's large population, uncontrolled building, and history of seismic activity. The findings suggest that earthquakes are viewed as a severe hazard by the people.

Fig. 5. Level of Public Concern Regarding Earthquakes in Dhaka City.

This figure 6 indicates that people have differing views on the usefulness of traditional building construction methods in minimizing earthquake damage. While some respondents felt conventional techniques offer minimal protection, the majority expressed indifferent or unfavorable opinions. This suggests a rising realization that enhanced building techniques and technology, such as seismic isolation systems, are important for increased earthquake resistance.

Fig. 6. Public Perception of the Effectiveness of Conventional Building Construction During Earthquakes.

B. Discussion

The collected data indicate that Seismic Isolation Pad technology can reduce major earthquake damage in Dhaka City, consistent with previous studies showing that base isolation reduces seismic forces and structural displacement in low- to moderate-seismic regions [3], [4]. All respondents (100%) had experienced or witnessed earthquakes, reflecting high public concern, which aligns with seismic hazard assessments identifying Dhaka as high-risk [2]. The majority supported seismic isolation as an effective safety measure, consistent with earlier research on its practicality in developing countries [4], while Rahman et al. noted that adoption in Bangladesh remains limited despite recognized technical benefits [1]. Strong support for mandatory earthquake safety measures (83.9%) reflects national discussions on enforcing building codes [5]. Key challenges identified include cost, awareness, technical expertise, weak enforcement, and retrofitting difficulties, consistent with prior findings [1], [3]. These results suggest that, with proper guidelines and government support, seismic isolation can significantly enhance building safety in Dhaka [1], [4].

IV. CONCLUSION

This study emphasizes how Seismic Isolation Pad technology could greatly improve building safety and lessen earthquake damage in Dhaka. A public survey showed that while people are very worried about earthquake risks and support mandatory safety rules, most are not familiar with seismic isolation methods. These findings align with earlier research [1]–[5], which confirms that base isolation successfully decreases earthquake forces and building movement, especially in areas

with low to moderate seismic activity. In conclusion, the research indicates that with the right policies, technical standards, and efforts to raise public awareness, seismic isolation technology can be a valuable strategy for strengthening earthquake resilience in Bangladesh's urban centers the importance of the work or suggest applications and extensions.

A. Limitations

This study has several limitations. The sample size was relatively small (30 respondents), and participants were primarily private university students, which may not fully represent the broader population of Dhaka. Data collection relied solely on online surveys, potentially excluding individuals without internet access. Additionally, the study did not include field measurements or structural simulations to quantify the precise effectiveness of seismic isolation pads in real-world buildings.

B. Suggestions

Future research should involve larger, more diverse samples, including residents from different socio-economic and occupational backgrounds, to improve generalizability. Incorporating field studies, structural modeling, and simulation analyses can provide quantitative evidence of seismic isolation performance. Public awareness campaigns, technical training programs, and stronger enforcement of building codes are recommended to facilitate the adoption of seismic isolation technology. Policymakers should consider integrating seismic isolation into building regulations to enhance urban earthquake resilience.

APPENDIX

1. What is your age group?

31 responses

2. What is your gender?

31 responses

3. What is your current occupation?

31 responses

4. Have you ever experienced an earthquake in Dhaka?

31 responses

5. Have you heard about Seismic Isolation Pad technology used for building safety?

31 responses

6. Are you familiar with your safety measures during an earthquake?

31 responses

7. In case of an earthquake, what will be your initial action to protect yourself?

31 responses

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8. Do you think earthquake safety measures should be mandatory for all buildings in Dhaka city (residential, commercial, and public buildings)?

31 responses

10. How concerned are you about earthquakes in Dhaka city?

31 responses

11. Do you think normal building construction methods can reduce damage during earthquakes?

31 responses

31 responses

31 responses

31 responses

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Rahman, M. S. Islam, and M. R. Hossain, "Status of Base Isolation Applications in Bangladesh," 2023.
- [2] T. M. Al-Hussaini et al., "Neo-deterministic seismic hazard assessment studies for Bangladesh," 2022.
- [3] A. B. M. S. Islam et al., "Effect of base isolation on buildings in Dhaka," 2010.
- [4] A. B. M. S. Islam et al., "Seismic base isolation for buildings in regions of low to moderate seismicity," 2012.
- [5] M. A. Noor, "After Narsingdi's jolt, a national push for seismic resilience is overdue," *The Daily Star*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.thedailystar.net/narsingdi-seismic-resilience>. Accessed: 03 Jan. 2026.